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TEST-COST-SENSITIVE CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS WITH EXPERT BRANCHES

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ABSTRACT

It has been proven that deeper convolutional neural networks (CNN) can result in better accuracy in many problems, but this accuracy comes with a high computational cost. Also, input instances have not the same difficulty. As a solution for accuracy vs. computational cost dilemma, we introduce a new test-cost-sensitive method for convolutional neural networks. This method trains a CNN with a set of auxiliary outputs and expert branches in some middle layers of the network. The expert branches decide to use a shallower part of the network or going deeper to the end, based on the difficulty of input instance. The expert branches learn to determine: is the current network prediction is wrong and if the given instance passed to deeper layers of the network it will generate right output; If not, then the expert branches stop the computation process. The experimental results on standard dataset CIFAR-10 show that the proposed method can train models with lower test-cost and competitive accuracy in comparison with basic models.

KEYWORDS

Test-Cost-Sensitive Learning; Deep Learning; CNN with Expert Branches; Instance-Based Cost

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Facial Expression Detection for video sequences using local feature extraction algorithms

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ABSTRACT

Facial expression image analysis can either be in the form of static image analysis or dynamic temporal 3D image or video analysis. The former involves static images taken on an individual at a specific point in time and is in 2-dimensional format. The latter involves dynamic textures extraction of video sequences extended in a temporal domain. Dynamic texture analysis involves short term facial expression movements in 3D in a temporal or spatial domain. Two feature extraction algorithms are used in 3D facial expression analysis namely holistic and local algorithms. Holistic algorithms analyze the whole face whilst the local algorithms analyze a facial image in small components namely nose, mouth, cheek and forehead. The paper uses a popular local feature extraction algorithm called LBP-TOP, dynamic image features based on video sequences in a temporal domain. Volume Local Binary Patterns combine texture, motion and appearance. VLBP and LBP-TOP outperformed other approaches by including local facial feature extraction algorithms which are resistant to gray-scale modifications and computation. It is also crucial to note that these emotions being natural reactions, recognition of feature selection and edge detection from the video sequences can increase accuracy and reduce the error rate. This can be achieved by removing unimportant information from the facial images. The results showed better percentage recognition rate by using local facial extraction algorithms like local binary patterns and local directional patterns than holistic algorithms like GLCM and Linear Discriminant Analysis. The study proposes local binary pattern variant LBP-TOP, local directional patterns and support vector machines aided by genetic algorithms for feature selection. The study was based on Facial Expressions and Emotions (FEED) and CK+ image sources.

KEYWORDS:

Local binary patterns on TOP Volume Local Binary Patterns(VLBP)

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Machine-Learning Estimation of Body Posture and Physical Activity by Wearable Acceleration and Heartbeat Sensors

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ABSTRACT

We aimed to develop the method for estimating body posture and physical activity by acceleration signals from a Holter electrocardiographic (ECG) recorder with built-in accelerometer. In healthy young subjects, triaxial-acceleration and ECG signal were recorded with the Holter ECG recorder attached on their chest wall. During the recording, they randomly took eight postures, including supine, prone, left and right recumbent, standing, sitting in a reclining chair, sitting in chairs with and without backrest, and performed slow walking and fast walking. Machine learning (Random Forest) was performed on acceleration and ECG variables. The best discrimination model was obtained when the maximum values and standard deviations of accelerations in three axes and mean R-R interval were used as feature values. The overall discrimination accuracy was 79.2% (62.6-90.9%). Supine, prone, left recumbent, and slow and fast walk were discriminated with >80% accuracy, although sitting and standing positions were not discriminated by this method.

KEYWORDS

Accelerometer, Holter ECG, Posture, Activity, Machine learning, Random Forest, R-R interval

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ROBUST IMAGE WATERMARKING METHOD USING WAVELET TRANSFORM

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a robust watermarking method operating in the wavelet domain for grayscale digital images is developed. The method first computes the differences between the watermark and the HH1 sub-band of the cover image values and then embed these differences in one of the frequency sub-bands. The results show that embedding the watermark in the LH1 sub-band gave the best results. The results were evaluated using the RMSE and the PSNR of both the original and the watermarked image. Although the watermark was recovered perfectly in the ideal case, the addition of Gaussian noise, or compression of the image using JPEG with quality less than 100 destroys the embedded watermark. Different experiments were carried out to test the performance of the proposed method and good results were obtained.

KEYWORDS

Watermarking, data hiding, wavelet transform, frequency domain

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FREE- REFERENCE IMAGE QUALITY ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK USING METRICS FUSION AND DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on no-reference image quality assessment(NR-IQA)metrics. In the literature, a wide range of algorithms are proposed to automatically estimate the perceived quality of visual data. However, most of them are not able to effectively quantify the various degradations and artifacts that the image may undergo. Thus, merging of diverse metrics operating in different information domains is hoped to yield better performances, which is the main theme of the proposed work. In particular, the metric proposed in this paper is based on three well-known NR-IQA objective metrics that depend on natural scene statistical attributes from three different domains to extract a vector of image features. Then, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) based dominant eigenvectors method is used to select the most relevant image quality attributes. These latter are used as input to Relevance Vector Machine (RVM) to derive the overall quality index. Validation experiments are divided into two groups; in the first group, learning process (training and test phases) is applied on one single image quality database whereas in the second group of simulations, training and test phases are separated on two distinct datasets. Obtained results demonstrate that the proposed metric performs very well in terms of correlation, monotonicity and accuracy in both the two scenarios.

KEYWORDS

Image quality assessment, metrics fusion, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), dominant eigenvectors, dimensionality reduction, Relevance Vector Machine (RVM)

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